

Coding Sample: Survey Responses (Q4)

ID	Q4: Anonymized responses	Q4: Code 1	Q4: Code 2 (optional)	Q4: Code 3 (optional)	Q4: Code 4 (optional)
1	"We are a squad of specialists with each his own specialty. Sometimes we depend on the specialist who knows more of the prioritized stories."	skills and knowledge			
2	"There will always be some uncertainties (e.g. operational incidents) and a product owner with changing requirements."	bugs or incidents	requirements refinement		
3	"Too many dependencies between teams and platforms, too many team "islands" with own priorities"	task dependencies	organizational alignment		
4	"It is important to have a very highly motivated team and build up teamwork"	team commitment	team maturity		
5	"When higher management shares our vision in digitalizing the bank, it would be a lot easier to accomplish our goals. We struggle with changes in management and budget cuts."	organizational alignment	organizational stability	executive support	
6	"The overhead of ING's security policies with regard to delivering critical software. The controls are there and are working to certain extent, however not everything works properly or is fully operational and that causes delay in our delivery."	project security			
7	"There is a constant shift in teammembers (unvoluntarily) leaving ING. Also the dependency on other teams and bureaucratic process seems to always create delays."	team stability	task dependencies	organizational politics	
8	"Organizational bureaucracy, lack of alignment of dependencies between teams and terrible infrastructure to move to PRD among others."	organizational politics	task dependencies	unreliable infrastructure	
9	"Proper refinement and understanding of complexity is really important at the start of a feature and involving all stakeholders at this point. "	refinement	user involvement		
10	"Each developer should write clean code with proper exception handling and then test the code using different frameworks. This makes production delivery more predictable."	lack of code quality	insufficient testing		
11	"Maturity in Agile delivery, ownership of product, discipline within squad"	agile maturity	team commitment		
12	"Coordination problems within our team. Half of our team is located in India."	geographical distribution			

This overview presents a coding sample for survey question 4: "In your experience, what factors (beyond the estimation process) affect the timeliness of your team's epic deliveries?". Each author is allowed to assign at least one and up to four codes to each response.